

Advances in the field of free space optical communications and the application of adaptive optics at Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias

E. Reyes-Rodríguez^{a,b}, R. Sánchez-Negrín^a, J. Socas-Negrín^{a,c}, J. Ortega-Rodríguez^a, K. Martín-Chinea^a, J.F. Hernández-Cabrera^a, F. Gracia-Témich^a, L.F. Rodríguez-Ramos^a, H. García-Vázquez^a, R. Melgar-Hernández^a, A. Alonso-Sánchez^a, D. Portero-Rodríguez^a, and N. Martínez-Rey^d

^aInstituto de Astrofísica de Canarias, E- 38205 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain

^bDepartamento de Astrofísica, Universidad de La Laguna, E-38206 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain

^cDepartamento de Ingeniería, Universidad de La Laguna, E-38206 La Laguna, Tenerife, Spain

^dAdvanced Instrumentation and Technology Centre, Research School of Astronomy and Astrophysics, Australian National University, Mount Stromlo Observatory, Cotter Road, Weston Creek, ACT 2611, Australia

ABSTRACT

Free Space Optical Communications (FSOC) has evolved into a very active research field integrating Gaussian beam propagation through the atmosphere, adaptive optics (AO) for turbulence correction, and quantum entanglement applications for optical links. Since the beginning of this century, the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC) has participated in several optical communications experiments, contributing to pioneering missions such as SILEX, OICETS and LADEE (ESA, NASDA, NASA).

The two high-altitude, top quality astronomical observatories operated by the IAC in the Canary Islands, separated by 144 km, provide a perfect test bench for the evaluation of FSOC terminals under real atmospheric conditions. In this work, we present the development of hardware and software solutions for an AO system based on a Shack–Hartmann wavefront sensor. This system is being developed for optical communication applications in collaboration with several industrial partners: SENER, INDRA, FYLA, IDOM and Thales Alenia.

The results obtained will be crucial for the next phases of the projects, which aim to extend the technology to space-based scenarios. Specifically, the experience gained in designing, aligning, and operating long-distance ground-to-ground FSOC links will serve as a foundation for establishing optical communication channels between ground stations and satellites in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) and Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO).

Keywords: Free Space Optical Communications, Adaptive Optics, Shack–Hartmann wavefront sensor, Atmospheric turbulence, Optical ground station, LEO/GEO satellite links

1. INTRODUCTION

Free Space Optical Communications (FSOC) have emerged as a highly promising technology for high capacity data transmission, providing fiber-like bandwidths without the need for physical cables [15, 10]. FSOC systems transmit information through modulated laser beams, enabling extremely high data rates over long distances with low latency and minimal electromagnetic interference. This capability has led to a growing interest in applications ranging from terrestrial point-to-point links to deep-space communications and satellite systems [14, 13]. Compared to conventional radio-frequency (RF) links, FSOC offers several advantages, including a large unlicensed spectrum, higher security due to narrow beam divergence, and reduced payload weight for satellite

Further author information: (Send correspondence to E.R-R)

E.R-R.: E-mail: ereyes@iac.es

applications [16]. Furthermore, FSOC terminals can be deployed rapidly with a lower infrastructure cost, which is particularly relevant for geographically complex regions such as the Canary Islands, our test environment.

Despite these advantages, FSOC links face significant challenges due to their reliance on the propagation of light through the atmosphere, which is a major limiting factor for link performance. Absorption and scattering by molecules and aerosols cause power attenuation, which varies with weather conditions, wavelength, and distance [3]. Additionally, atmospheric turbulence induces random variations in the refractive index along the propagation path, leading to phase distortion, beam wander, and intensity scintillation [2]. These turbulence-induced effects result in signal fading, increased bit error rates and temporal fluctuations in received power, which are particularly severe for long horizontal links [20]. Several models have been developed to quantify these effects, including the Kolmogorov turbulence model, Rytov variance calculations, and statistical beam-propagation simulations [2].

To overcome these challenges and stabilize the performance of the optical link, Adaptive Optics (AO) systems have been introduced into FSOC terminals. Originally developed for astronomical imaging, AO systems measure the incoming wavefront in real time using sensors such as Shack–Hartmann [21] detectors and apply corrective deformations via deformable mirrors [22]. When integrated into FSOC systems, AO can significantly reduce the effects of beam wander and scintillation, improve the coupling efficiency into single-mode receivers, and stabilize the received signal [1, 19, 26]. Recent experimental studies have demonstrated the efficacy of AO, achieving reliable multi-gigabit performance over long terrestrial horizontal links, including successful wavefront correction experiments over highly turbulent 53 km paths [11]. Furthermore, contemporary theoretical work has validated AO performance through detailed models of turbulence mitigation [23], reinforcing the feasibility of achieving long-distance FSOC. This modeling is complemented by other studies validating the performance gains achieved by AO systems in typical near-ground links [19]. The growing demand for robust, high-throughput satellite communication systems has further driven AO development for ground-to-space links, showing its viability for pre-compensation in GEO feeder links [4], where it can reduce signal losses by up to 10 dB [12]. This field is supported by sophisticated models to optimize the necessary compensation [18, 7].

The Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC) has a long history of participation in optical communication experiments, contributing to pioneering missions such as SILEX, OICETS, and LADEE (ESA, NASDA, NASA) [17, 25, 5]. The two high-altitude, top-quality astronomical observatories operated by the IAC in Tenerife and La Palma, separated by 144 km, provide a perfect laboratory for evaluating FSOC terminals under real atmospheric conditions [20]. This combination of long link distance, varying meteorological conditions and high-quality telescopes allows for detailed studies of beam propagation, turbulence mitigation, and adaptive optics performance.

In this work, we present the development of hardware and software solutions for an AO system based on a Shack–Hartmann wavefront sensor. The system is designed for inter-island FSOC applications and is being developed in collaboration with several industrial partners, including SENER, INDRA, FYLA, IDOM, Navantia, and Thales Alenia. The experiments focus on the characterization of turbulence effects, system alignment strategies, and real-time wavefront correction techniques for link improvement. The experience gained from these studies is expected to form the basis for extending FSOC technology to ground-to-space scenarios, including optical links between ground stations and satellites in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) and Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO). Such developments will enable high-capacity, low-latency communication channels for advanced applications. By combining experimental, computational, and system-design approaches, this study aims to demonstrate the feasibility of long-distance inter-island FSOC links and to provide a roadmap for future satellite communication applications.

This paper is organized as follows: in Sec. 2 we describe the theoretical models; Sec. 3 details the Optical Design of the FSOC system; Sec. 4 presents the Software developed for alignment and AO compensation; finally, Sec. 6 offers a Discussion and Next Steps, and Sec. 7 summarizes the Conclusions.

2. THEORETICAL MODELS

The performance of FSOC on Earth is fundamentally limited by atmospheric turbulence. This phenomenon introduces spatial and temporal phase and amplitude fluctuations to the optical beam, resulting in both beam wander (tip-tilt) and beam quality degradation (higher-order aberrations). The primary objective of this section is to establish the mathematical framework used to quantify these effects, thus justifying the design requirements of the implemented AO system.

2.1 Refractive Index Structure and the Kolmogorov Model

Atmospheric turbulence is caused by variations in temperature and pressure leading to fluctuations in the refractive index (n). The index is modeled as

$$n(\mathbf{r}) = n_0 + n_1(\mathbf{r}), \quad (1)$$

where $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ is the random fluctuating component. The severity of the turbulence is quantified primarily by the Refractive Index Structure Constant (C_n^2), expressed in $\text{m}^{-2/3}$.

The standard theoretical approach is based on the Kolmogorov theory [24], which models the statistics of these fluctuations. For the highly elevated, long-distance link implemented in this work, between Tenerife and La Palma, the model must consider certain criteria for C_n^2 , such as non-uniformity:

- Elevated Path Profile: While horizontal links at ground-level assume a high value of C_n^2 , our link operates at an altitude of approximately 2400 meters above sea level. At this elevation, the atmosphere is generally more stable and the turbulence is significantly weaker than within the boundary layer.

- Path Averaging: For inter-island links, the severity of the turbulence must be described by the path-averaged C_n^2 or, more accurately, by integrating the constant along the path. The experimental data will confirm whether the conditions align more closely with the typical Hufnagel-Valley (HV) or Greenwood models often used for astronomical sites, rather than severe horizontal ground-level models.

2.2 Fried's Coherence Length (r_0): The AO Design Metric

Fried's coherence length [8], r_0 , is one of the most critical parameter in the design of an AO system. Physically represents the diameter of an ideal telescope aperture over which the root-mean-square (RMS) phase distortion of the incoming wavefront is approximately 1 rad^2 . Simply put, r_0 defines the characteristic spatial scale of atmospheric turbulence — that is, the size of the smallest "cell" or "patch" of the atmosphere that an AO system must correct.

The general expression for r_0 for a path of length L and wave number $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ is:

$$r_0 = \left[0.423 k^2 \int_0^L C_n^2(z) dz \right]^{-3/5} \quad (2)$$

Crucially, because our link is quasi-horizontal but highly elevated, and given the long distance, we often simplify the model by assuming an average C_n^2 along the path for design purposes, which yields a value of r_0 large enough to justify the use of AO. The calculated value of r_0 directly dictates the requirements for the AO hardware:

- Actuator Density: The separation between the actuators on the DM must be comparable to r_0 to ensure adequate sampling of the distorted wavefront.

- WFS Sub-aperture Size: The diameter of the microlenses in the Shack-Hartmann WFS should be matched to r_0 .

Figure 1 shows the theoretically obtained values of r_0 as a function of distance. Given the high altitude, we anticipate a generally higher r_0 (weaker turbulence) compared to sea-level routes, which is beneficial for system performance but still requires AO due to the extreme length of the link. We have assumed three possible atmospheric conditions: optimal ($1 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$), standard ($1 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$) and unfavorable ($1 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$). Assuming these extreme conditions and taking into account that the typical C_n^2 values measured at the observatories are of the order of $1 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$ (measured vertically), it is expected that the measured values will fall within the range shown in the graphs. However, we must bear in mind that an r_0 of 25 cm and similar values is not a situation that would be expected in reality for a horizontal link, but has been considered to analyze the effect of different levels of turbulence.

Figure 1. Fried parameter r_0 for a wavelength of 1550 nm with respect to distance for different values of C_n^2 . Blue represents optimal conditions ($C_n^2 = 1 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$), purple represents standard conditions ($C_n^2 = 1 \cdot 10^{-15} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$), and salmon represents unfavorable conditions ($C_n^2 = 1 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^{-2/3}$). In addition, the value for the endpoint of interest, after 144 km, is indicated.

2.3 Greenwood Frequency (f_G): The AO Speed Metric

In addition to the spatial scale (r_0), the temporal dynamics of the turbulence must be characterized. The Greenwood frequency [9], f_G , defines the temporal cutoff frequency of the turbulence, which determines the minimum required bandwidth of the AO control loop.

The Greenwood frequency, which governs the necessary speed of the AO system, is approximated by:

$$f_G \approx 0.4 \frac{V_{\perp}}{r_0}, \quad (3)$$

where V_{\perp} is the average wind speed transverse to the optical path. For example, at the Observatorio de Izaña, Tenerife, the average wind speed is approximately $V_{\perp} \sim 10 \text{ m/s}$. For a typical atmospheric coherence length of $r_0 = 0.6 \text{ cm}$, Eq. (3) yields:

$$f_G \approx 0.4 \frac{10 \text{ m/s}}{0.006 \text{ m}} \approx 667 \text{ Hz}. \quad (4)$$

For effective correction, the AO closed-loop bandwidth should be greater than f_G , with larger factors improving correction for fast turbulence. The long distance and the wind conditions between the islands result in a non-trivial f_G , making the high-speed processing capability of the AO control software a critical design requirement.

3. OPTICAL CONFIGURATION

The optical configuration of the inter-island FSOC link is divided into two principal subsystems: the Transmitter, responsible for launching a high-power, collimated beam; and the Receiver that incorporates the Adaptive Optics (AO) system for real-time wavefront correction. The design must accommodate the extreme path length of 144 km and the severe turbulence conditions quantified in Section 2 (where r_0 can drop as low as 0.60 cm in standard conditions). Therefore, the receiver must utilize an AO system with high spatial and temporal bandwidth to maximize the coupling efficiency of the received signal into the single-mode fiber (SMF) for detection.

3.1 Transmitter in JKT, La Palma: Optical Configuration

The transmitter terminal (Figure 2), located at the Jacobus Kapteyn Telescope (JKT) in La Palma, is responsible for launching the high-power, diffraction-limited beam across the atmosphere. The design is based on an architecture operating in the Short-Wave Infrared (SWIR) band, which offers high data rates and favorable atmospheric transmission properties.

- **Wavelength (λ):** The system utilizes a fiber optic laser operating at a transmission wavelength of 1590 nm.
- **Aperture Diameter (D):** The output beam is expanded and launched using a Cassegrain telescope with an aperture diameter of 250 mm.
- **Optical Path:** The laser fiber optic (single mode, 9 microns) is inserted into a 45 mm focal length lens (achromatic doublet). From here, it will be collimated to a 60 mm focal length lens and will exit through the 250 mm aperture telescope.
- **Power Output:** The system is capable of high-power operation to overcome significant atmospheric path loss and scintillation effects. The maximum continuous wave (CW) power output is 8.58 W and the maximum modulated output power is 7.70 W (at 50% duty cycle/ 10 Hz).

Figure 2. Assembly of the transmitter installed in the JKT telescope, La Palma. The image shows the fiber injection into the lens system and the attachment to the telescope.

The alignment of the transmitter is a non-trivial process crucial for maximizing the received power on the 144 km distant receiver. The key steps include:

- Collimation Verification: The output of the telescope is collimated by verifying the beam over a short-distance range (fifty to one hundred meters) using a SWIR camera.
- Focus and Divergence Control: Fine-tuning the focus is used to intentionally magnify the beam, which is often necessary to compensate for large-scale beam wander caused by tip/tilt aberrations over long terrestrial links.

3.2 Receiver in OGS, Tenerife: Optical Configuration

The receiver terminal is installed in the Coudé room of the Optical Ground Station (OGS) 1 m telescope in Tenerife (Figure 3) and constitutes the core of the AO system. Its fundamental function is to capture the incoming wavefront perturbed by the 144 km atmospheric path, correct the resulting aberrations in real time, and maximize the signal coupling into a Single-Mode Fiber (SMF) for data acquisition. The AO system is designed to satisfy the rigorous spatial resolution requirement set by the Fried's coherence length, r_0 , which is calculated to be as

Figure 3. Assembly of the receiver installed in the OGS telescope, Tenerife.

small as 0.60 cm under standard conditions for this link.

The optical configuration shown in Figure 4 corresponds to the setup used in the first experimental campaign, focused on the fundamental performance characterization of the high-order corrector. During this initial phase, the system relies exclusively on the Deformable Mirror (DM) for all corrections, including low-order modes such as tip and tilt. In subsequent phases and campaigns, additional subsystems, such as a dedicated Fast Steering Mirror (FSM), will be integrated to offload Tip-Tilt and optimize low-order aberration rejection, thus achieving the full target performance of the AO system.

After the OGS focal plane, the beam is collimated by lens L_1 ($f = 500$ mm). It then propagates through a pupil relay system that reduces the 1 m entrance pupil to a 20 mm beam, matching the clear aperture of the active components.

This configuration specifically represents the first experimental phase, which includes and operates all AO hardware except the FSM. The AO loop is controlled by a dedicated control system software, described in Section 4.

The key components of the AO subsystem are:

- **Deformable Mirror (DM):** The main wavefront corrector consists of a 192 actuator DM positioned in a conjugate pupil plane, providing high-order aberration correction.
- **Wavefront Sensor (WFS):** A Shack-Hartmann WFS samples the corrected beam using a 15×15 microlens array and a 640×512 pixel detector with a $15 \mu\text{m}$ pixel pitch. It provides the wavefront error signal for the control loop.
- **Beam Steering:** A flat mirror is used in this phase to simulate the future position of the FSM. Currently, tip-tilt correction is performed by the DM, which stabilizes the beam against atmospheric wander. In future, an FSM will replace the flat mirror, and tip-tilt correction will be decoupled from the DM.

Figure 4. Diagram of the receiver installed in the OGS telescope, Tenerife. The image shows all the elements of the adaptive optics system and details the focal lengths of the lenses used.

This 15×15 microlens and 192-actuator configuration is not arbitrary; it is sized to meet the minimum spatial requirement under the most stringent atmospheric conditions anticipated for the link. This corresponds to a design value for the Fried parameter of $r_0 = 0.6$ cm (referenced at $\lambda = 550$ nm).

For signal detection and diagnostics, the following components are included or planned for installation in upcoming campaigns:

- **Coupling and Fiber:** The main communication signal is coupled into a single-mode fiber (SMF) through a 45 mm lens (L_4). The coupled power is monitored using an external power meter, allowing simultaneous measurement of free space and coupled signals after accounting for beamsplitter (BS) losses.
- **SWIR Camera:** A 640×512 pixel short-wave infrared camera ($20 \mu\text{m}$ pixel pitch) is used for diagnostic purposes, including spot monitoring and turbulence statistics.
- **Calibration Source:** An internal 1550 nm laser provides a reference beam for system alignment and influence matrix calibration.

The entire AO loop is managed by a sophisticated, custom-developed software control System. This system is the core of the operation, implementing a closed-loop sequence where the information flow is strictly defined:

1. The WFS measures the current wavefront aberrations and produces an error signal.
2. The control system software processes this signal using the pseudoinverse of the influence matrix to compute the correction commands.
3. These commands are sent in real time to the DM, which applies the corresponding deformations to correct the wavefront.

The operation and user interface of this control software are detailed in Section 4.

4. CONTROL SYSTEM SOFTWARE

The control system software is designed to manage, calibrate, and monitor a complete AO system. Its core is based on a closed-loop control system, in which wavefront aberrations are measured using a SHWFS and corrected by applying the appropriate commands to a DM.

The main objective of the system is to keep the wavefront as flat as possible in real time, ensuring accurate and

stable correction of optical disturbances.

The graphical user interface (GUI) is organized into four main sections that form the general structure of the system (Figure 5):

1. The deformable mirror display (Figure 5.a) shows the layout of all actuators, their current position and the defined displacement limits, always respecting the physical limitations of the mirror).
2. The deformable mirror control (Figure 5.b) allows direct modification of the DM's operating conditions, for example:
 - Place the mirror in a neutral position ("flat").
 - Load a file with predefined settings.
 - Manually adjust the displacement (piston) of a specific actuator.
3. The control system panel (Figure 5.c) contains the adjustable variables that directly affect the behavior of the control loop and the correction quality of the AO system.
4. Wavefront sensor display (Figure 5.d) shows the microlenses and centroids detected in each subaperture. Depending on the operating mode, additional information is also displayed, such as the RMS error between the measured and reference centroids.

Figure 5. Graphical user interface (GUI) for controlling the deformable mirror and adaptive optics.

In the last panel, we can find various parameters. Some of the most relevant ones are highlighted below:

- **Integral Gain:** Defines the response speed and aggressiveness of the correction in closed loop.
- **Forgetting Factor:** Limits the accumulation of old errors in the integrator. It acts as a low-pass filter, improving stability against noise or slow drift.
- **Max Actuator Stroke:** Sets the maximum displacement limit allowed for each actuator, protecting the mirror from saturation or damage.
- **Close RTC Loop:** Checkbox that enables or disables the AO system's real-time control loop.
- **Enable Tip-Tilt Correction:** Allows you to enable or disable global lateral displacement correction (tip and tilt modes) of the beam.
- **ROI Radius:** Defines the radius (in pixels) of the area used for centroid calculation in each WFS sub-aperture.
- **Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) Lower Bound:** Parameter that stabilizes the inversion of the influence matrix when applying the pseudoinverse. Typical values between 15 and 25 achieve an adequate balance between robustness and sensitivity.

In addition, another function defined in this system is calibration. Calibration is an essential step for the AO control loop to function correctly.

The process begins with obtaining the reference centroids, which represent the ideal position of each subaperture in the absence of aberrations (for example, using a flat mirror).

Subsequently, each DM actuator is individually excited to measure how its movement affects the wavefront detected by the WFS. These responses are collected to form the influence matrix (M), which describes the linear relationship between actuators (a) and sensor measurements (s).

$$s = M \cdot a \quad (5)$$

Once M has been obtained, a SVD is applied to calculate its pseudoinverse (M^+). This decomposition of M consists of the following:

$$M = U \Sigma V^T, \quad (6)$$

where U and V are orthogonal matrices and Σ is a diagonal matrix with the singular values ordered from largest to smallest. Calculating the pseudoinverse as:

$$M^+ = V \Sigma^+ U^T \quad (7)$$

Matrix 7 is used during the closed loop operation, in each iteration of the control:

$$a_{n+1} = (1 - \lambda) a_n + G_i M^+ (s_{\text{ref}} - s_n), \quad (8)$$

where:

- a_n are the deformable mirror commands,
- s_n are the current WFS measurements,
- s_{ref} are the reference centroids,
- λ is the forgetting factor, which partially attenuates the influence of the previous command a_n , preventing excessive accumulation of historical errors and improving dynamic stability,
- M^+ is the pseudoinverse of the influence matrix, and
- G_i is the integral gain, which adjusts the intensity or speed with which the calculated corrections are applied.

Thus, the system continuously updates the mirror positions until the residual wavefront error is minimized.

5. SIMULATIONS

This section presents the results of a preliminary numerical simulation of OOMAO [6] used to validate the design and projected performance of the Adaptive Optics (AO) system against the requirements. The objective was to confirm that the high-order correction capabilities of the 192-actuator Deformable Mirror (DM) are sufficient to achieve a high coupling efficiency into the Single-Mode Fiber (SMF) under the most challenging turbulence conditions of the 144 km link.

The simulations were performed using the system's exact specifications:

- **Wavelength to be coupled:** 1550 nm
- **Telescope aperture:** 1 m
- **Central obscuration:** 36%
- **Coupling aperture:** 10.4 μm
- **Sensor pixels on the most restrictive axis:** 512 px
- **Deformable mirror:** 16×16 (256 actuators, 192 functional actuators)
- **Microlenses array:** 15×15

Table 1. Results obtained from simulations for a wavelength of 1550 nm and for open-loop and closed-loop coupling indices, as well as the improvement between the two. The table includes references to the annex for each case.

Fried parameter [cm]	Open-loop coupling	Closed-loop coupling	Improvement index	Reference
15	0.4167	0.5720	1.3726	A.1
10	0.1940	0.5726	2.9523	A.2
7	0.1020	0.5706	5.5966	A.3
4	0.0193	0.5606	29.0488	A.4
1	0.0189	0.4110	21.7020	A.5
0.6	0.0084	0.2521	30.1470	A.6

- **Link distance:** 144 km
- **Focal length of the receiving telescope:** 4786.6 mm
- **Iterations:** 1000, 200 open loop + 800 closed loop

Table 1 summarizes the key performance metrics projected for a specific turbulence condition, demonstrating the critical improvement achieved by the AO system in increasing the coupling efficiency. For our purposes, we have focused on conditions where r_0 is between 0.6 cm and 15 cm, which are normal for observatories, but without going to ideal extremes since this is a horizontal link.

6. DISCUSSION AND NEXT STEPS

The development of the adaptive optics (AO) receiver for the Tenerife–La Palma free-space optical communication (FSOC) link represents a crucial milestone in demonstrating the feasibility of long-distance optical links under realistic atmospheric conditions. The optical design, control software and integration strategy described in this work collectively form the foundation for validating high-order wavefront correction over long propagation paths.

The results from theoretical modeling and preliminary simulations indicate that the proposed AO system can maintain fiber-coupling efficiency and signal stability even under standard turbulence regimes ($r_0 \approx 0.6$ cm), with an expected improvement factor of more than one order of magnitude compared to open-loop operation. These findings support the feasibility of achieving high-throughput data transmission using adaptive compensation in near-ground optical links.

From a system-level perspective, the architecture implemented at the OGS telescope has proven to be both adaptable and scalable. The decision to allocate tip–tilt correction to the deformable mirror (DM) in the first campaign simplified early commissioning, enabling a complete validation of the AO control chain before introducing additional components such as a Fast Steering Mirror (FSM). The optical configuration, optimized for diffraction-limited performance within the spatial coherence constraints of the atmospheric channel, ensures that the system can operate effectively under a wide range of turbulence conditions.

Following the successful laboratory validation of the full AO loop, the project has now entered its field implementation phase at the OGS telescope in Tenerife. The current objectives focus on the characterization of on-sky performance, including Strehl ratio, coupling efficiency and power stability across varying turbulence conditions. These campaigns will provide the first comprehensive assessment of the system’s performance under real atmospheric propagation over the 144 km Tenerife–La Palma path.

Beyond the immediate goal of establishing a stable horizontal link between Tenerife and La Palma, this work contributes to the broader objective of developing adaptive optical ground stations for future space communication networks. The experience gained from this system will serve as a critical stepping stone toward implementing AO-assisted feeder links for Low Earth Orbit (LEO) and Geostationary Orbit (GEO) satellites. In this context, the infrastructure developed at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC) can serve as a scalable testbed for future European and international optical communication initiatives.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents the design, development and integration strategy for a high-speed Adaptive Optics (AO) receiver, developed at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC), intended for the 144 km Free Space Optical Communication (FSOC) link between Tenerife and La Palma. The primary objective is to stabilize link performance against the severe atmospheric turbulence that limits long-distance terrestrial FSOC.

The theoretical framework established the demanding design requirements for the channel: a characteristic spatial scale (Fried parameter, r_0) as low as 0.60 cm and a temporal requirement (Greenwood frequency, f_G) of

approximately 667 Hz. To meet these challenges, the system relies on a 192 actuator Deformable Mirror (DM) and a dedicated Shack-Hartmann Wavefront Sensor, along with custom-developed control software capable of high-frequency closed-loop operation.

The successful integration of the optical configuration and the control system at the OGS Observatory represents the critical initial validation of the full AO loop. This long-distance inter-island channel serves as a unique and scalable testbed globally. The forthcoming experimental campaigns—focused on quantifying the Strehl ratio, single-mode fiber coupling efficiency, and power stability—will pave the way for the IAC’s future role in high-capacity ground-to-space optical links with satellites in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) and Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The research and development described in this paper were carried out at the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC), thanks to funding from the European Union’s recovery and resilience funds (NextGenerationEU) and “Hub Nacional de Excelencia en Comunicaciones Cuánticas, al Ministerio para la Transformación Digital y de la Función Pública a la Unión Europea-NextGenerationEU”. ER-R would like to acknowledge the vital contribution by Cabildo de Tenerife for their support in the “Capacitación Tecnológica” project, which was instrumental to this work. DP-R. is “personal contratado predoctoral del Programa de Astrofísicos Residentes del IAC”.

References

- [1] Isiaka A. Alimi and Paulo P. Monteiro. “Revolutionizing Free-Space Optics: A Survey of Enabling Technologies, Challenges, Trends, and Prospects of Beyond 5G Free-Space Optical (FSO) Communication Systems”. In: *Sensors* 24.24 (2024). ISSN: 1424-8220. DOI: [10.3390/s24248036](https://doi.org/10.3390/s24248036). URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/24/24/8036>.
- [2] L. C. Andrews and R. L. Phillips. *Laser Beam Propagation Through Random Media*. 2nd. Bellingham, WA: SPIE Press, 2005. ISBN: 9780819459482.
- [3] Aniceto Belmonte and Joseph Khan. “Performance of synchronous optical receivers using atmospheric compensation techniques”. In: *Optics Express* 16.18 (Sept. 2008), p. 14151. DOI: [10.1364/OE.16.014151](https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.16.014151).
- [4] Aurélie Montmerle Bonnefois et al. “Ground to GEO Satellites Optical Feeder Links: status and challenges”. In: *Laser Congress 2024 (ASSL, LAC, LS&C)*. Optica Publishing Group, 2024, LsTh3C.3. DOI: [10.1364/LSC.2024.LsTh3C.3](https://doi.org/10.1364/LSC.2024.LsTh3C.3). URL: <https://opg.optica.org/abstract.cfm?URI=LSC-2024-LsTh3C.3>.
- [5] Don M. Boroson et al. “Overview and results of the Lunar Laser Communication Demonstration”. In: *Free-Space Laser Communication and Atmospheric Propagation XXVI*. Ed. by Hamid Hemmati and Don M. Boroson. Vol. 8971. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. Mar. 2014, 89710S, 89710S. DOI: [10.1117/12.2045508](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2045508).
- [6] R. Conan and C. Correia. “Object-oriented Matlab adaptive optics toolbox”. In: *Adaptive Optics Systems IV*. Ed. by Enrico Marchetti, Laird M. Close, and Jean-Pierre Vran. Vol. 9148. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. Aug. 2014, 91486C, p. 91486C. DOI: [10.1117/12.2054470](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2054470).
- [7] O. J. D. Farley, M. J. Townson, and J. Osborn. “FAST Simulation of Ground-Space Optical Links with Adaptive Optics”. In: *Imaging and Applied Optics Congress 2022 (3D, AOA, COSI, ISA, pcAOP)*. Optica Publishing Group, 2022, OF2B.1. DOI: [10.1364/AOA.2022.OF2B.1](https://doi.org/10.1364/AOA.2022.OF2B.1). URL: <https://opg.optica.org/abstract.cfm?URI=AOA-2022-OF2B.1>.
- [8] D. L. Fried. “Optical Resolution Through a Randomly Inhomogeneous Medium for Very Long and Very Short Exposures”. In: *Journal of the Optical Society of America (1917-1983)* 56.10 (Oct. 1966), p. 1372. DOI: [10.1364/JOSA.56.001372](https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSA.56.001372).
- [9] D. P. Greenwood. “Bandwidth specification for adaptive optics systems.” In: *Journal of the Optical Society of America (1917-1983)* 67 (Mar. 1977), pp. 390–393. DOI: [10.1364/JOSA.67.000390](https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSA.67.000390).
- [10] Hamid Hemmati. *Deep Space Optical Communications*. 2006.
- [11] Yannik Horst et al. “Tbit/s line-rate satellite feeder links enabled by coherent modulation and full-adaptive optics”. In: *Light: Science & Applications* 12.1, 153 (Dec. 2023), p. 153. DOI: [10.1038/s41377-023-01201-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41377-023-01201-7).
- [12] Ilija R. Hristovski et al. “Pre-distortion adaptive optics for optical feeder links: simulations and performance analyses”. In: *Opt. Express* 32.12 (June 2024), pp. 20976–20991. DOI: [10.1364/OE.521494](https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.521494). URL: <https://opg.optica.org/oe/abstract.cfm?URI=oe-32-12-20976>.

- [13] H. Kaushal, V. K. Jain, and S. Kar. *Free Space Optical Communication*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2017. ISBN: 978-3-319-63952-6. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-63953-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-63953-3).
- [14] Hemani Kaushal and Georges Kaddoum. “Optical Communication in Space: Challenges and Mitigation Techniques”. In: *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* 19.1 (2017), pp. 57–96. DOI: [10.1109/COMST.2016.2603518](https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2016.2603518).
- [15] Debbie Kedar and Shlomi Arnon. “Urban Optical Wireless Communication Networks: The Main Challenges and Possible Solution”. In: *IEEE Communications Magazine* 42.5 (Jan. 2004), S2–S7. DOI: [10.1109/MCOM.2004.1299334](https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2004.1299334).
- [16] Mohammad Ali Khalighi and Murat Uysal. “Survey on Free Space Optical Communication: A Communication Theory Perspective”. In: *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* 16.4 (2014), pp. 2231–2258. DOI: [10.1109/COMST.2014.2329501](https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2014.2329501).
- [17] B. Laurent and O. Duchmann. “SILEX project: the first European optical intersatellite link experiment”. In: *Free-Space Laser Communication Technologies III*. Ed. by David L. Begley and Bernard D. Seery. Vol. 1417. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. June 1991, pp. 2–12. DOI: [10.1117/12.43737](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.43737).
- [18] Yalin Li et al. “Multistep ahead atmospheric optical turbulence forecasting for free-space optical communication using empirical mode decomposition and LSTM-based sequence-to-sequence learning”. In: *Frontiers in Physics* 11, 1070762 (Jan. 2023), p. 1070762. DOI: [10.3389/fphy.2023.1070762](https://doi.org/10.3389/fphy.2023.1070762).
- [19] Andres Ivan Martinez et al. “Self-adaptive integrated photonic receiver for turbulence compensation in free space optical links”. In: *Scientific Reports* 14.1, 20178 (Aug. 2024), p. 20178. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-024-70726-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-70726-7). arXiv: [2406.05402](https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.05402) [[physics.optics](https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.05402)].
- [20] Jorge Rosano Nonay et al. “Horizontal free-space optical link with CubeISL over 143 km”. In: *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.* 16.5 (May 2024), pp. 593–601. DOI: [10.1364/JOCN.518271](https://doi.org/10.1364/JOCN.518271). URL: <https://opg.optica.org/jocn/abstract.cfm?URI=jocn-16-5-593>.
- [21] Ben Platt and Roland Shack. “History and Principles of Shack-Hartmann Wavefront Sensing”. In: *Journal of Refractive Surgery* 17 (Sept. 2001), S573–S577. DOI: [10.3928/1081-597X-20010901-13](https://doi.org/10.3928/1081-597X-20010901-13).
- [22] F. Roddier, ed. *Adaptive Optics in Astronomy*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 1999.
- [23] Larry B. Stotts and Larry C. Andrews. “Adaptive optics model characterizing turbulence mitigation for free space optical communications link budgets”. In: *Optics Express* 29.13 (June 2021), p. 20307. DOI: [10.1364/OE.430554](https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.430554).
- [24] V. I. Tatarski, R. A. Silverman, and Nicholas Chako. “Wave Propagation in a Turbulent Medium”. In: *Physics Today* 14.12 (Jan. 1961), p. 46. DOI: [10.1063/1.3057286](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3057286).
- [25] Morio Toyoshima et al. “Ground-to-satellite optical link tests between Japanese laser communications terminal and European geostationary satellite ARTEMIS”. In: *Free-Space Laser Communication Technologies XVI*. Ed. by Steve Mecherle, Cynthia Y. Young, and John S. Stryjewski. Vol. 5338. International Society for Optics and Photonics. SPIE, 2004, pp. 1–15. DOI: [10.1117/12.530138](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.530138). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.530138>.
- [26] Shane M. Walsh et al. “Demonstration of 100 Gbps coherent free-space optical communications at LEO tracking rates”. In: *Scientific Reports* 12, 18345 (Oct. 2022), p. 18345. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-022-22027-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-22027-0).

APPENDIX A. SIMULATIONS OF THE COUPLING FOR A 144 KM LINK WITH THE CHARACTERISTICS DESCRIBED IN SECTION 5.

A.1. $r_0 = 15$ cm

Figure 6. Simulation of the Point Spread Function (PSF) for single-mode fiber coupling (red circle). The figure shows the incident wavefront under atmospheric turbulence defined by a Fried parameter $r_0=15$ cm adjusted to a wavelength of 550 nm with and without adaptive optics and a for a coupling wavelength of 1550 nm.

A.2. $r_0 = 10$ cm

Figure 7. Simulation of the Point Spread Function (PSF) for single-mode fiber coupling (red circle). The figure shows the incident wavefront under atmospheric turbulence defined by a Fried parameter $r_0=10$ cm adjusted to a wavelength of 550 nm with and without adaptive optics and a for a coupling wavelength of 1550 nm.

A.3. $r_0 = 7$ cm

Figure 8. Simulation of the Point Spread Function (PSF) for single-mode fiber coupling (red circle). The figure shows the incident wavefront under atmospheric turbulence defined by a Fried parameter $r_0=7$ cm adjusted to a wavelength of 550 nm with and without adaptive optics and a for a coupling wavelength of 1550 nm.

A.4. $r_0 = 4$ cm

Figure 9. Simulation of the Point Spread Function (PSF) for single-mode fiber coupling (red circle). The figure shows the incident wavefront under atmospheric turbulence defined by a Fried parameter $r_0=4$ cm adjusted to a wavelength of 550 nm with and without adaptive optics and a for a coupling wavelength of 1550 nm.

A.5. $r_0 = 1$ cm

Figure 10. Simulation of the Point Spread Function (PSF) for single-mode fiber coupling (red circle). The figure shows the incident wavefront under atmospheric turbulence defined by a Fried parameter $r_0=1$ cm adjusted to a wavelength of 550 nm with and without adaptive optics and a for a coupling wavelength of 1550 nm.

A.6. $r_0 = 0.6$ cm

Figure 11. Simulation of the Point Spread Function (PSF) for single-mode fiber coupling (red circle). The figure shows the incident wavefront under atmospheric turbulence defined by a Fried parameter $r_0=0.6$ cm adjusted to a wavelength of 550 nm with and without adaptive optics and a for a coupling wavelength of 1550 nm.